

Comparison of manufacturer tolerance of different preformed orthodontic arch wires

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To measure manufacturer tolerance of preformed rectangular orthodontic arch wires in terms of cross sectional, vertical and transverse dimensions.

Materials and Methods: One hundred and twenty preformed archwires were selected from six various brands in both stainless steel and nickel titanium. Transverse dimensions were measured at both intercanine and intermolar area by photocopying the wires and intra brand comparison was done by using portable USB microscope. Cross sectional dimensions were measured with micrometer while vertical discrepancy was measured at anterior and intermolar region with leaf gauges. One sample t test used to evaluate intra-brand tolerance in wires.

Results: Db orthodontics stainless steel wires were the most oversized while Dentaureum nickel titanium wires were the most undersized in terms of wires height. In terms of wire width, Ortho Organizers stainless steel wires were most oversized while Db orthodontics nickel titanium wires were the most under sized wires. Considering transverse dimension, intercanine width within a brand was found uniform while 3M stainless steel and Dentaureum nickel titanium wires showed statistically significant discrepancy at intermolar area in intrabrand comparison. Statistically significant vertical discrepancy at intermolar region was found in four out of six brands of stainless steel wires and only one brand of nickel titanium wires.

Conclusion: Preformed orthodontic wires can be oversized or undersized in cross sectional dimensions with vertical discrepancy mostly present in stainless steel wires. Manufacturer makes uniform intercanine width but intermolar width is usually expanded from the intended arch form.

Keywords: *Manufacturer tolerance, preformed rectangular arch wires, cross-sectional dimensions*

INTRODUCTION

Andrew's preadjusted edgewise brackets were based on the concept that only straight wires should be used during the treatment.¹ However, over the period of time it became evident that certain degree of wire bending is necessary to attain final occlusal outcomes.^{2,3} These shortcomings in straight wire concept were partly due to limitation of not engaging full dimensional archwires in the bracket slot and partly due to individual variations in crown morphology⁴⁻⁸, bracket positioning errors^{5,9} and manufacturer tolerance of brackets and wires.^{3,10-15}

The availability of higher torqued brackets than Andrews prescriptions to some extent have solved the problem of torque loss through wire play.¹⁶ With experience, variables like crown morphology and bracket positioning can be predicted and managed, however, the manufacturer tolerance of brackets and wires are hard to predict until or unless the orthodontist keep specialized tools to measure dimensions of brackets and wires.

A lot is written on manufacturer tolerance in cross-sectional dimensions of preformed rectangular wires.^{3, 17,18} However there are two other important aspects of preformed rectangular wires that are totally being overlooked which are transverse and vertical dimensions. Inaccuracies in transverse dimension of the archwires can cause arch length discrepancies, lack of inter arch coordination issues leading to cusps hanging and premature contacts which in severe cases can have dire consequences on patient dental health.¹⁹⁻²¹ Inaccuracies in vertical dimension of archwires can cause either open bite or deep bite depending upon direction of wire placement which will ultimately lead to cant of the occlusal plane and poor aesthetic outcome of treatment.

Manufacture tolerance of preformed stainless steel (SS) wires can easily be corrected for vertical and transverse discrepancies or compensated for cross-sectional problems by wire bending due to wires good formability and torsional properties of SS. On contrary, nickel titanium (NiTi) wires because of high spring back, have poor formability and torsional properties, so any attempt to correct or compensate manufacture tolerance in these wires is very difficult in clinical setting.²²

The purpose of this study was to measure manufacture tolerance of preformed orthodontic wires in terms of cross sectional, vertical and transverse dimensions.

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MATERIAL AND METHODS

The sample comprised of one hundred and twenty wires with nominal size of 0.019" x 0.025" from six different commercially available brands. From each manufacturer, ten SS and ten NiTi wires in ovoid archform were selected. Two manufacturers supplied both SS and NiTi wires in individual packing, four brands were supplied in a pack of 10 while in one brand both SS and NiTi wires were randomly taken from a pack of hundred (Table 1).

To check whether manufacturers make consistent

archform in transverse dimension, each of the preformed archwires of different brands were photocopied in 1:1 on separate graph papers and compared with rest of the wires of that brand. The one template on which maximum number of wires coincides was taken as master archform and it was supposed that this archform was one which the manufacturer was intending to make. Transverse tolerance of rest of the wires at intercanine and inter first molar area was measured in millimeters under magnification using portable USB microscope (Supereyes, CN) and a transparent ruler (Figure 1, 2).

Table1: Grades of pterygium

Table 1: Orthodontic wires tested					
Manufacture	Company Headquate	Abbreviation used	Material	Packing	Dimension (inches)
Db Orthodontics	West Yorkshire, UK	Dbortho	NITi /Pseudoelastic	Pack of 10	0.019x0.025
Db Orthodontics	West Yorkshire,UK	Dbortho	SS	Pack of 10	0.019x0.025
3 M Unitek	Monrovia, Calif, USA	3 M	NITi/ Thermoelastic	Individual Packing	0.019x0.025
3 M Unitek	Monrovia, Calif, USA	3 M	SS		0.019x0.025
Dentaurum	Newtown, Pa, USA	DT	NITi / Superelastic	Pack of 10	0.019x0.025
Dentaurum	Newtown, Pa, USA	DT	SS	Pack of 10	0.019x0.025
Natural	Deerfield Beach, Florida,USA	NT	NITi / Superelastic	Individual Packing	0.019x0.025
Natural	Deerfield Beach – Florida,USA	NT	SS	Individual Packing	0.019x0.025
Ortho Organizers	San Marcos, Calif, USA	OO	NITi / Superelastic	Pack of 10	0.019x0.025
Ortho Organizers	San Marcos, Calif, USA	OO	SS	Pack of 10	0.019x0.025
Henry Schein	Melville, NY, USA	HS	NITi / Superelastic	Pack of 100	0.019x0.025
Henry Schein	Melville, NY, USA	HS	SS	Pack of 100	0.019x0.025

Inter canine area was taken at 10 mm arch depth while intermolar area was taken 30 mm arch depth (Figure 1). Separate intra brand comparison of transverse discrepancy was measured for SS and NiTi wires. As thermal NiTi wires were also included in this study so they were heated to mouth temperature by air heater

before photocopying and also for vertical or transverse measurements.

Cross sectional dimensions of the wires were measured in inches with a digital micrometer (Mitutoyo, JP) having accuracy of ± 0.00005 " (Figure 3). For cross-sectional dimensions, each wire was measured at middle

Figure 1: Photocopy of arch form on graph paper. Intercanine width was taken at 10 mm arch depth while inter molar area was taken at 30 mm.

Figure 2: Deviation in transverse dimensions: Archwires was measured in millimeters under magnification using portable USB microscope (Supereyes, CN) and a transparent ruler.

of anterior segment and at one point on both right and left sides of buccal segments at intermolar area. The average values of height and width of the wire were then taken. Vertical tolerance in the wire was measured by placing the wire on a flat surface and sliding leaf gauges between the wire and flat surface without causing vertical movement of the wire. Although size of leaf gauges was mentioned on them, but digital micrometer was used to measure the combined height of leaf gauges. Vertical

discrepancy if present was measured in millimeters in both anterior and buccal segments (Figure 4, 5). The data was entered and analyzed by SPSS 21 software. Descriptive statics were done for all the variables and one sample t test used to evaluate intrabrand tolerance in the wires. p value less than 0.05($p < 0.05$) was taken as significant.

Figure 3: Digital micrometer (Mitutoyo, JP) for measurement of cross sectional dimensions.

Figure 4: Leaf gauges of different thickness in millimeter.

Figure 5: Measurement of vertical discrepancy by sliding leaf gauges under the wire placed on a flat surface

Results

Descriptive statistics and one sample t test for cross sectional wire height for both SS and NiTi are given in table 2. Descriptive statistics show that in terms of wire height manufacturers sell both oversized and undersized wires in either SS or NiTi. Db orthodontics SS wires

were the most oversized wires while Dentaurem NiTi wires were the most undersized. In terms of wires cross sectional width (Table 3) Ortho Organizer SS were the most oversized wires while Db Orthodontics NiTi was the most undersized wires. Cross sectional width of Henry Schein SS was closest to standardized dimensions.

Descriptive statistics and one sample t test for transverse discrepancy at intercanine and intermolar region are shown in table 4 & 5. One sample t test show no statistically significant wires discrepancy at intercanine region while 3M SS and Dentaurem NiTi wires show statistically significant discrepancy at intermolar region. Mean value of transverse discrepancy for Henry Schein SS wires though not statistically significant but maximum discrepancy of 2.5 mm was noted at intermolar region with these wires while maximum discrepancy at intercanine region was noted 1.25 mm in Ortho organizer SS wires. Vertical discrepancy in the wires at molar region is shown in table 6. NiTi wires show less vertical discrepancy than SS wires. Only Henry Schein NiTi wires showed statistically significant discrepancy at molar region. Four out of six manufacturer SS wires had statistically significant vertical discrepancy at molar region.

Table 2: Cross sectional height (in inches) of the different orthodontic wires

Company	Wire	Property	Standard Value	N	Mean	SD	T	Sig	Mean Difference
Db Ortho	NiTi	Height	.019	10	.0190000	.00003333	.000	1.000	.00000000
Db Ortho	SS	Height	.019	10	.0190450	.00004378	3.250	.010*	.00004500
3M	NiTi	Height	.019	10	.019	.000	.818	.434	.000015
3M	SS	Height	.019	10	.0189550	.0004972	-2.862	.019*	.00004500
Dentaurem	NiTi	Height	.019	10	.0188100	.00009661	-6.219	.000*	-.00019000
Dentaurem	SS	Height	.019	10	.0189700	.00004216	-2.250	.051	-.00003000
Natural	NiTi	Height	.019	10	.0190400	.00009068	1.395	.196	.00004000
Natural	SS	Height	.019	10	.0190300	.00008882	1.068	.313	.00003000
OO	NiTi	Height	.019	10	.0189800	.00007149	-.885	.399	-.00002000
OO	SS	Height	.019	10	.0190650	.00008515	2.414	.039*	.00006500
HS	NiTi	Height	.019	10	.0190300	.00011832	.802	.443	.00003000
HS	SS	Height	.019	10	.0189550	.00014804	-.961	.362	-.00004500

Table 3: Width in inches of the different orthodontic wires

Company	Wire	Property	Standard Value	N	Mean	SD	T	Sig	Mean Difference
Db Ortho	NiTi	Width	.025	10	.0248	.00003	-18.974	.000*	-.00020
Db Ortho	SS	Width	.025	10	.0250200	.00009487	.667	.522	.00002000
3M	NiTi	Width	.025	10	.0249	.000	-6.862	.000*	-.00010
3M	SS	Width	.019	10	.0250	.000	.818	.434	.000015
Dentaurum	NiTi	Width	.025	10	.0249	.00013	-3.280	.010*	-.00014
Dentaurum	SS	Width	.025	10	.0250400	.00006583	1.922	.087	.00004000
Natural	NiTi	Width	.025	10	.0249	.00011	-3.115	.012*	-.00011
Natural	SS	Width	.025	10	.0249500	.00008498	-1.861	.096	-.00005000
OO	NiTi	Width	.025	10	.0250	.00009	-1.793	.107	-.00005
OO	SS	Width	.025	10	.0250350	.00004743	2.333	.045*	.00003500
HS	NiTi	Width	.025	10	.0250	.00016	-.692	.506	-.00004
HS	SS	Width	.025	10	.0250250	.00013994	.565	.586	.00002500

* Sign show significance difference. P<0.05 was taken significant

Table 4: Transverse discrepancy in millimeters at intercanine area

Company	Wire	Property	Standard Value	N	Mean	SD	T	Sig	Mean Difference
Db Ortho	NiTi	T-canine	.00	10	.0000	.00000	-	-	-
Db Ortho	SS	T-canine	.00	10	.0000	.00000	-	-	-
3M	NiTi	T-canine	.00	10	.0000	.00000	-	-	-
3M	SS	T-canine	.00	10	.17500	.373609	1.481	.173	.175000
DT	NiTi	T-canine	.00	10	.0000	.00000	-	-	-
Dentaurum	SS	T-canine	.00	10	.10000	.316228	.750	.472	.075000
Natural	NiTi	T-canine	.00	10	.0000	.00000	-	-	-
Natural	SS	T-canine	.00	10	.00000	.000000	-	-	-
OO	NiTi	T-canine	.00	10	.0000	.00000 ^a	-	-	-
OO	SS	T-canine	.00	10	.22500	.477988	1.489	.171	.225000
HS	NiTi	T-canine	.00	10	.0000	.00000 ^a	-	-	-
HS	SS	T-canine	.00	10	.17500	.373609	1.481	.173	.175000

* Sign show significance difference. P<0.05 was taken significant

Table 5: Transverse discrepancy in millimeters at intermolar area									
Company	Wire	Property	Standard Value	N	Mean	SD	T	Sig	Mean Difference
Db Ortho	NiTi	T-molar	.00	10	.0000	.00000	-	-	-
Db Ortho	SS	T-molar	.00	10	.0000	.00000	-	-	-
3M	NiTi	T-molar	.00	10	.0000	.00000	-	-	-
3M	SS	T-molar	.00	10	.4750	.48947	2.390	.041*	.47500
Dentaurum	NiTi	T-molar	.00	10	.3750	.63246	2.423	.038*	.37500
Dentaurum	SS	T-molar	.00	10	.2000	.63246	1.000	.343	.20000
Natural	NiTi	T-molar	.00	10	.0000	.00000	-	-	-
Natural	SS	T-molar	.00	10	.1750	.37361	1.481	.173	.17500
OO	NiTi	T-molar	.00	10	.0000	.00000	-	-	-
OO	SS	T-molar	.00	10	.3500	.74722	1.481	.173	.35000
SH	NiTi	T-molar	.00	10	.1250	.39528	1.000	.343	.12500
SH	SS	T-molar	.00	10	.5500	.83997	2.071	.068	.55000

* Sign show significance difference. P<0.05 was taken significant

Table 6: Vertical discrepancy in millimeters at intermolar									
Company	Wire	Property	Standard Value	N	Mean	SD	T	Sig	Mean Difference
Db Ortho	NiTi	VD	.00	10	.00000	.000000	-	-	-
Db Ortho	SS	VD	.00	10	.1931000	.15674782	3.896	.004*	.19310000-
3M	NiTi	VD	.00	10	.00000	.000000	-	-	-
3M	SS	VD	.00	10	.2007000	.14490230	4.380	.002*	.20070000
DT	NiTi	VD	.00	10	.01020	.032255	1.000	.343	.010200
Dentaurum	SS	VD	.00	10	.0889000	.17569952	1.600	.144	.08890000
Natural	NiTi	VD	.00	10	.02030	.036050	1.781	.109	.020300
Natural	SS	VD	.00	10	.0940000	.11793030	2.521	.033*	.09400000
OO	NiTi	VD	.00	10	.00000	.00000 ^a	-	-	-
OO	SS	VD	.00	10	.1753000	.20264750	2.736	.023*	.17530000
HS	NiTi	VD	.00	10	.16000	.188522	2.684	.025*	.160000
HS	SS	VD	.00	10	.1809000	.26973009	2.121	.063	.18090000

* Sign show significance difference. P<0.05 was taken significant

DISCUSSION

Cross sectional dimensions of preformed rectangular wires are of fundamental importance as they affect the torque play and eventually the final buccolingual inclination of teeth.^{14,23} The present study found out that cross-sectional dimensions of various commercial brands of rectangular orthodontic wires both in SS and NiTi were either oversized or undersized from the nominal or manufacturer claimed values. Similar findings were reported by numerous studies done on wire cross section.^{3,15,24} An undersized wire will increase the torque play yielding poor final occlusal and aesthetic outcome, while an oversized wire will increase the friction resistance thus hindering sliding mechanics.^{3,25,26}

In the present study, in terms of cross sectional height 3M wires were the most undersized in SS wires and the difference from nominal dimension was statistically significant. Whereas a study conducted by Dolci¹⁵ measuring rectangular segments of four 0.019 x 0.025 inch wires found that 3M wires were oversized in height with a statistically significant value. The difference in results can be due to method of measuring wire dimension as Dolci used surface electron microscope in his study but interestingly width of 3M wires reported in Dolci study and present study were similar and was exactly in manufacture prescribed dimension.

Sernetz¹⁸ advocated standardization of orthodontic products and his efforts led to formation of DIN (Deutsches Institut für Normung e.v.) standards in Germany. In DIN standards orthodontic wires should not have more than +0.01 mm tolerances in both height and width dimensions. If results of cross section dimension of orthodontic wires in present study are analyzed according to DIN standards none of wire measured was out of tolerance limit in both height and width.

The mean transverse discrepancy in both NiTi and SS wires was not significant in the intercanine area but 3M SS and Dentaurum Niti wires were significantly expanded at the intermolar area. Expanded 0.019x0.025-inch SS wires will always alter the archform of natural dentition while same dimension NiTi wires if left for a longer time will then alter the archform.²⁸ As the preformed maxillary archwires are 1-2 mm wider than mandibular archwires a further increase in maxillary arch dimension will result in poor inter arch coordination leading to faulty occlusal outcome and unstable final finish.²⁹⁻³² Though controversial³³ but it has mostly been reported^{28,34,35} that preformed archwires are wider than natural archform. Therefore, if by chance the clinician places an expanded

archform, it will further increase the stability of the final results.

Vertical discrepancy was noted in the molar region only and was mostly seen in SS wires. Apart from manufacturer tolerance, vertical discrepancy in SS wires can occur during packing and handling of the wires. Henry Schein NiTi wires also showed statically significant vertical discrepancy. As these wires were super elastic and well packed so there is little possibility for extreme bending during packing or handling and vertical discrepancy was due to manufacturer tolerance.

Manufacturer tolerance of orthodontic arch wires should not be taken as granted and if combined with manufacturer tolerance of orthodontic brackets have far reaching consequences in final aesthetic and occlusal outcome. Manufacturer should make efforts to increase precision in manufacturing process and also should improve the packing of wires especially stainless steel to avoid distortions of the wires during delivery and handling.

CONCLUSION

1. Preformed orthodontic wires can be oversized or undersized in cross sectional dimension from the manufacturer claimed values.
2. Vertical discrepancy was present in molar region mostly in stainless steel wires.
3. Manufacturer makes uniform intercanine width but intermolar width is usually expanded from the intended arch form.

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